

FIC-FIGHTERS Deliverable D2.7

Preliminary environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) Report

Summary:

Deliverable 2.7, the first preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for the FIC-FIGHTERS project scheduled for M18, presents an initial evaluation of environmental impacts and highlights the primary environmental hotspots within the phosphogypsum valorization pathways. This early analysis establishes a baseline for more detailed scenario assessments and optimization measures in later stages of the project. The assessment will reach its completion by month 40, with the submission of Deliverable 2.8, which constitutes the full Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) report.

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Table of Contents

Executive summary	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 LCA in waste valorization, with a Focus on FIC-FIGHTERS Project	6
2 Evaluating phosphogypsum valorization routes through LCA	10
2.1 Step 1 - Goal and scope	10
2.1.1 Goal definition	10
2.1.2 Scope definition	10
2.2 Step 2 - Life cycle inventory (LCI) of each evaluated route.....	14
2.2.1 Procedure for Life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis	14
2.2.2 Life cycle inventory (LCI) sources.....	15
2.2.3 Life cycle inventory (LCI) Data Quality.....	16
2.2.4 NaOH Route LCI: Inputs and Outputs	17
2.2.5 AMONI Route LCI: Inputs and Outputs.....	18
2.3 Step 3 – LCA Impact assessment across evaluated routes	19
2.4 Step 4 - Interpretation	19
3 Life Cycle Assessment across the evaluated routes	19
3.1 Hotspots identification	19
3.1.1 NaOH Route.....	20
3.1.2 AMONI Route.....	22
3.2 Climate change impact	23
3.2.1 NaOH route.....	23
3.2.2 AMONI route	24
4 Interpretation	24
4.1 Comparative scenarios	25
4.1.1 NaOH route: Climate change impact	25
4.1.2 NaOH route: Water use impact	26
4.1.3 AMONI route: Climate change impact.....	27
4.2 Comparative LCA to the baseline (business-as-usual stockpiles).....	29
4.3 Sensitivity Analysis	30
4.3.1 NaOH route: Water use impact	30
4.3.2 NaOH route: Carbon Removal Efficiency (CRE)	31
5 Circularity performance assessment	32
5.1 Theoretical foundation	32
5.2 Circularity assessment indicators	32
5.2.1 Key circular actions	34
6 LCA preliminary conclusions	35
7 References	36

List of Figures

Figure 1 FIC-FIGHTERS process flow chart and products from NaOH route	8
Figure 2 FIC-FIGHTERS process flow chart and products from AMONI route	8
Figure 3 Overview of the LCA workflow for PG waste valorisation	11
Figure 4 LCA system boundaries for the alkaline conversion of Phosphogypsum using pure NaOH	12
Figure 5 LCA system boundaries for the conversion of Phosphogypsum through AMONI Route	13
Figure 6 Simplified procedure for data inventory analysis	15
Figure 7 LCI data sources and flow to Impact Assessment	15
Figure 8 Settings to modelling environmental impact	19
Figure 9 Overall NAOH route hotspots environmental relative contribution	20
Figure 10 Reaction 1 environmental relative contribution	21
Figure 11 AMONI route environmental relative contributions overall process	22
Figure 12 Climate change impact associated with processing 1 kg of PG	23
Figure 13 Climate change impact associated with processing 1 kg of PG	24
Figure 14 Climate change impact associated with production of 1 kg of CaCO ₃	25
Figure 15 Four evaluated scenarios - Climate change impact	26
Figure 16 Water use impact associated with production of 1 kg of CaCO ₃	27
Figure 17 Climate change impact associated with production of 1 kg of PCC	28
Figure 18 Climate change impact associated with production of 1 kg of Ammonia sulfate	28
Figure 19 Climate change impact associated with production of 1kg of Valuable metals	28
Figure 20 Comparative environmental impact categories vs the PG stockpiles under the same FU	29
Figure 21 Water use impact in four evaluated scenarios	30
Figure 22 Carbon removal efficiency vs the electricity carbon intensity	31
Figure 23 Circularity performance indicators	33

List of Tables

Table 1 Europe Phosphogypsum stockpiles location (FIC -FIGHTERS pilots)	6
Table 2 LCA contribution to guide decision-making in the FIC-FIGHTERS project	9
Table 3 LCI data quality criteria	16
Table 4 NaOH Route LCI - Inputs & Outputs	17
Table 5 AMONI Route LCI - Inputs & Outputs	18
Table 6 LCA scenarios for the NaOH route: evaluating the carbonation (Reaction 2)	25
Table 7 Indicators to track circularity and sustainability design	33
Table 8 Circular Economy Butterfly Diagram - key actions	34

Executive summary

The purpose of Deliverable D2.7 is to present the preliminary environmental profiles and impact scores derived from the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the proposed chemical routes for phosphogypsum (PG) waste valorization. These routes aim to upgrade PG for use in the production of construction materials, detergents, fertilizers and related applications. D2.7 (“Report on the Environmental LCA Assessment”), together with reports D2.9 & D2.10 (“Economic LCC Analysis”) and D2.12 (“Circular Economy Guidelines”), constitutes a comprehensive assessment framework for the FIC-Fighters supply chain. These deliverables collectively support the identification of sustainability gains and areas requiring further optimization at industrial scale.

This deliverable corresponds to Subtask 2.4.1 – Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), under Work Package 2: Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemical routes, which aims to optimise the two chemical processes developed in the project through a safe, sustainable, and circular approach. The LCA contributes directly to the WP2 objectives by quantifying and evaluating the potential environmental benefits of the proposed solutions compared to current industrial practices, thereby supporting the implementation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design methodology. It provides a scientific basis to identify environmental hotspots, assess trade-offs, and guide process optimisation and engineering design. In line with WP2 goals, the LCA also informs the economic and circularity assessments, helping to identify opportunities for resource efficiency, cost reduction, and risk mitigation, while ensuring compliance with sustainability, health, and safety principles across the project’s value chain.

This document provides a brief description of the methodological framework adopted under the life cycle perspective, along with a definition of the case studies to be analysed, namely, the NaOH Pure, and AMONI routes. It compiles the life cycle inventories, identifying key hotspots and proposing improved scenarios. A comparative analysis with conventional PG disposal practices highlights the potential environmental benefits and remaining challenges.

The deliverable is structured into 7 chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction provides an overview of the FIC-Fighters project, summarizing its objectives, main environmental challenges, and the expected benefits of the proposed valorization routes.

Chapter 2: Evaluating phosphogypsum valorization routes through LCA, presents the methodological framework adopted, highlighting the relevance of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach within the project context.

Chapter 3: LCA Impact Assessment and discussion, details the analysis and discussion of the results obtained from the assessment of the different valorization routes and scenarios.

Chapter 4: LCA Interpretation, includes the interpretation and comparative analysis of the evaluated scenarios and routes, identifying key insights and implications.

Chapter 5: Circularity Performance Assessment, introduces the evaluation of circularity indicators, emphasizing their relevance and alignment with ISO standards and the methodological approach applied.

Chapter 6: LCA Preliminary Conclusions, summarizes the initial conclusions and recommendations derived from the current evaluation. As a preliminary report, these insights will continue to be refined throughout the project’s development.

Chapter 7: References, lists all the bibliographic and reference materials consulted for the preparation of this deliverable.

1 Introduction

Phosphogypsum (PG) is generated during the "wet process" of phosphoric acid production, which is the most common route for producing phosphate fertilizers. In this process, the phosphate rock reacts with sulfuric acid, resulting in phosphoric acid (for fertilizers) and large amounts of PG as a waste.

Globally, estimates indicate that between 100 and 280 million tonnes of PG are produced annually [1], with Europe hosting several major production and storage sites. For every tonne of phosphoric acid produced, approximately 4.5 to 5.5 tonnes of PG are generated. Traditionally, PG has been considered a hazardous waste, leading to extensive stockpiles and associated environmental and regulatory challenges.

Across Europe, these PG repositories, whether legacies of past industrial activity or linked to ongoing fertilizer production, pose significant environmental management challenges, specific sites, such as those in Huelva (Spain), Barreiro (Portugal), and Kutina (Croatia), are the focus of both public and regulatory attention [2].

FIC-Fighters (Fair, Inclusive, Circular and Healthy cities), a research project funded by European commission, was launched in 2024 and it is running until 2028, the project involves 27 partners from 12 countries. Its goal is to develop and demonstrate innovative, circular processes for converting PG waste into commercial upgraded materials, which applications are in construction & building, detergents, and fertilisers sectors, as well as batteries and packaging.

The case studies currently defined under the FIC-Fighters project, which represent the specific locations considered in the scope of the project, are as follows:

Table 1 PG stockpiling locations addressed in the FIC-Fighters Project

Case Study	Country	Site (Location)
Case study N°1	Portugal	Barreiro
Case study N°2	Croatia	Kutina
Case study N°3	Serbia	Prahovo
Case study N°4	Romania	Turnu Măgurele
Case study N°5	North Macedonia	Veles
Case study N°6	Spain	Cartagena

1.1 LCA in waste valorization, with a Focus on FIC-FIGHTERS Project

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a holistic and comprehensive methodology for assessing the potential environmental impacts of a product or process in each stage of its life cycle, from the extraction of the materials to the management of the disposed product after its use (cradle-to-grave). Adherence to ISO standards 14040:2006 and 14044:2006 [3,4], ensures results are consistent, robust, and transparent, facilitating meaningful comparison of alternatives.

The importance of LCA in waste valorization lies in its ability to rigorously identify environmental hotspots, quantify impact reduction, and substantiate claims of circularity and resource optimization. In practice, LCAs have demonstrated how waste recovery routes (such as recycling, reuse, or conversion

to secondary products) can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, energy demand, resource depletion, and other environmental burdens compared to conventional disposal. By transforming what was formerly seen as waste into valuable resources, circular strategies anchored in LCA underpin both environmental and economic sustainability.

In the domain of phosphogypsum (PG) waste management, LCA studies have critically assessed a range of valorization approaches, including use in cement and construction materials, recovery of rare earth elements, and conversion to fertilizers, geopolymers, and chemical intermediates. Essaid Bilal et al. [5], conducted a comprehensive global review analyzing more than 65 phosphogypsum storage sites worldwide. Their work emphasizes the significant environmental risks posed by open stockpiles, mainly due to heavy metal leaching and contamination potential. A recent comparative LCA found that repurposing 1 kg of PG as a precursor for coal fly ash-based geopolymer reduced CO₂ emissions by 40%, energy consumption by 90%, and mineral resource extraction by 36% compared to conventional landfilling [6]. These results underscore both the potential for impactful environmental savings and the continued need for expanding LCA coverage to new valorization routes and industrial scales.

Smerigan et al. [7], focused on recovering rare earth elements from PG using innovative bioinspired adsorption technologies, integrating LCA with techno-economic analysis. Their findings show this can mitigate ecosystem quality and resource depletion impacts compared to conventional mining but might increase human health impacts due to chemical use. Profitability depends on scale and rare earth content, indicating further optimization is needed for environmental sustainability of these processes.

Given the complexity and scale of environmental issues, the drive to valorize PG as a secondary resource has gained momentum as part of circular economy initiatives. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is increasingly applied to quantitatively evaluate the environmental benefits and trade-offs of such valorization strategies, for example, converting PG into new products or resources (replacing raw materials for the industry).

At this stage in the project, a preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is being conducted on the products developed under Work Package 1 (WP1). This initial assessment aims to guide laboratory-scale efforts toward producing a sustainable set of intermediate products. The findings from this phase will feed into Deliverable D2.8, which will present the results from both valorization routes (WP3) and their integration into industrial products. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the updated process flow. The data workflow provided by the University of Sevilla and Åbo University for several lab-scale scenarios was used as the primary input for the preliminary results presented in this deliverable. However, further refinement of the data and LCA approach and calculations will be required to produce more accurate balances and, consequently, a more reliable assessment of the net environmental impact of the main valuable products.

Figure 1 FIC-FIGHTERS process flow chart and products from NaOH route

Figure 2 FIC-FIGHTERS process flow chart and products from AMONI route

In the context of phosphogypsum (PG) valorization, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) serves as a critical method for quantifying and comparing the broad environmental impacts associated with different management pathways. To guide effective decision-making in the FIC-Fighters project, the environmental LCA will be developed progressively throughout the project, and it is expected to deliver three main contributions (summarized in the table below):

Table 2 LCA contribution to guide decision-making in the FIC-FIGHTERS project

LCA Contribution	Key Outcomes	How It supports PG Valorization decisions
Setting Priorities	<p>Hotspot identification</p> <p>Quantifies which process steps, materials, or inputs are responsible for the largest environmental impacts (GHG, resource use, toxicity, etc.) in each pathway/scenario. Highlights where to focus immediate improvement or innovation efforts for the greatest system-wide benefit. At early design stage of the Project.</p>	<p>This allows prioritization of redesign efforts to address the dominant contributors to total environmental burden, thereby maximizing the effectiveness of mitigation strategies of the environmental footprint associated with PG valorization pathways.</p>
Choosing routes/pathways	<p>Comparative LCA analysis</p> <p>Provides side-by-side quantitative environmental comparisons between alternative valorization routes (NaOH route vs AMONI route). Includes scenarios/sensitivity analysis.</p>	<p>Objectively identifies the best-performing pathway(s) for minimizing impacts from the environmental point of view, assisting on the decision making to design the most sustainable option for PG management.</p>
Benchmarking	<p>Establishes comparison vs the baseline</p> <p>Calculates environmental impacts of the current approach (e.g., PG disposal or direct use) to set a reference point. Enables tracking of improvements, setting of ambitious reduction goals, and periodic re-assessment as changes are made along the project.</p>	<p>Target-setting for impact reduction as evidence to justify decisions from the environmental point of view.</p>

However, it is important to clearly describe beforehand the limitations of LCA in this specific context of PG valorization as the FIC-Fighters Project study cases:

- **Site-specific Risk Assessment:** LCA is not designed to fully address local, site-dependent risks such as: Groundwater pollution or leachate migration (depends on unique hydrogeology); Mobility of radionuclides or heavy metals in specific environments; Direct human health risks or worker exposures; Ecological impacts on nearby habitats (biodiversity, species health)
- **Detailed Toxicological Evaluation:** LCA databases use average toxicity factors but do not provide nuanced, location-specific health risk calculations (e.g., from airborne radon, trace metals or local water contamination).
- **Short-term/Acute effects:** LCA focuses on cumulative, long-term impacts, not rapid, acute events like accidental spills or one-off dust releases.
- **Regulatory compliance and monitoring:** Cannot ensure compliance with local legal or regulatory limits, nor replace the need for ongoing environmental and health monitoring in-situ.

2 Evaluating phosphogypsum valorization routes through LCA

Within FIC-Fighters Project, the aim is to use LCA's robust framework to identify environmental hotspots in three candidate PG valorization routes:

- First, the valorization routes using NaOH-rich sources:
 - Derived from Al-waste (Al-waste NaOH route)
 - Pure NaOH, derived route from the experimental work initially performed (pure NaOH route).

Therefore, a parallel assessment of the “NaOH pure route” will be included as a baseline scenario to establish an initial reference point for comparison in the current Deliverable D2.7.

- Second, phosphogypsum waste valorisation through the NH_3 treatments (AMONI route).

Following these standards, the methodology is structured within the following stepwise procedure:

2.1 Step 1 - Goal and scope

2.1.1 Goal definition

This deliverable (D2.7) serves as a starting point and will be fully completed and finalized by month 40 (D2.8). The objective of this preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is to explore and identify potential environmental hotspots associated with the chemical valorization of phosphogypsum (PG) waste, for the NaOH-based process (Route 1) and the NH_3 -based process (Route 2).

Given the preliminary nature of the data, results are indicative, and a full comparative LCA may change as more robust and comparable data become available after WP1 activities. The results at this stage will be used for internal decision support and process development internally for the project partners, rather than for public comparative assertions.

2.1.2 Scope definition

The scope of this preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is defined by a cradle-to-gate approach, encompassing all steps from the extraction and processing of primary raw materials: PG transport from its country of origin to facilities in Spain or Finland, up to the production of intermediate valorized products at the facility gate. Downstream activities such as the distribution, utilization, and end-of-life management of the final products are excluded at this stage, as the current analysis is focused on the early phases where environmental hotspots are likely to occur and where process development is still underway.

2.1.2.1 Functional Unit

The functional unit is set as **1 kg of processed PG waste (98% PG purity)**. This declared reference unit allows for direct and fair comparison across the different valorization scenarios and is particularly suited for early development stages, where market performance and application are not yet fully defined.

In subsequent development phases, the functional unit will be refined to reflect the actual performance or function of the final commercial product - for instance, by considering product specifications such as purity, composition or technical application. This adjustment will ensure that the assessment remains market-relevant and aligned with the products' end-use requirements and quality standards.

At this preliminary stage, life cycle inventory data and calculated impacts are scaled to this input quantity as a reference unit (1kg of PG). Where sufficient data are available, results (chapter 4) may also be

presented per kilogram of specific valorized product. In such cases, strict internal mass balancing is applied to maintain consistency and accuracy across all the calculations.

2.1.2.2 System Boundaries - FIC-FIGHTERS PG valorization routes

The LCA assessment aims to evaluate the valorisation of phosphogypsum (PG) waste into valuable raw materials for use in industries such as cement, detergents, and batteries. The LCA analysis will be carried out in three phases named here for clearance: Phase 1: Waste recovery and valorization LCA assesment; Phase 2: Downstream product LCA assessment; Phase 3: Full LCA assessment.

In the first stage (the project’s initial period, outlined in this deliverable D2.7) we quantify all burdens and benefits and calculate a preliminary net CO₂ balance for the two chemical treatment routes that converts PG from stockpiles into an industrially acceptable raw material with the properties required by the FIC-fighters’ industrial partners. In the second stage, together with our industrial partners, we will review the final product manufacturing processes and collect the necessary data to calculate the environmental benefits of applying the new materials provided by FIC-fighters, for example in the blending of new SCM-based concrete. Finally, for the final product and formulation tested, the associated burdens and benefits will be calculated, and a full environmental impact assessment will be carried out to determine the net benefit of PG valorisation; the same procedure will be applied to the other industrial applications.

Figure 3 Overview of the LCA workflow for PG waste valorisation

In the next section, the analysis is initiated by breaking down the two treatment pathways for PG waste. Each route is examined in terms of processing steps, inputs and outputs, energy and material requirements, and preliminary environmental impacts.

NaOH Route: Phosphogypsum waste valorization via alkaline (NaOH) conversion

PG waste is reacted with sodium hydroxide to produce portlandite, Ca(OH)₂. Subsequently, atmospheric CO₂ is captured and utilized in a carbonation reactor to transform portlandite into calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), promoting carbon sequestration and generating valuable industrial materials.

The preliminary LCA report uses pure NaOH as the base because the experimental design for Al-waste NaOH treatment is still being refined. Conditions and material flows for an accurate Life Cycle Inventory are being adjusted. The Al-waste NaOH route produces Katoite (Ca₃Al₂(OH)₁₂) and other by-products, which change material flows, reaction conditions, and environmental impacts. This detailed analysis will be conducted and included in the next report to ensure a comprehensive and accurate LCA.

Figure 4 LCA system boundaries for the alkaline conversion of Phosphogypsum using pure NaOH

Both background and foreground inputs and outputs, aligned with ISO 14040/14044 standards for LCA were included in the system boundaries (dashed):

- **Background System**

- Extraction and processing of raw materials, including NaOH, water, and any other auxiliary inputs used in the process.
- Energy Supply, production of energy carriers (e.g., electricity)
- Transportation of raw materials to the facility, and management of waste or by-products beyond the plant boundary.

- **Foreground System**

- Phosphogypsum valorization processes (Routes 1), including all on-site operations: energy and utility consumption, chemical reactions, emissions, and waste streams occurring within the facility.
- Route 1A: The chemical conversion of Phosphogypsum (PG) through NaOH addition to form portlandite, Ca (OH)₂, followed by the carbonation step using atmospheric CO₂ to produce calcium carbonate (CaCO₃).
- Energy usage to CO₂ capture is considered depending on the scenario.

AMONI route: Phosphogypsum waste valorization via ammonia (NH₃)-based conversion

Figure 5 LCA system boundaries for the conversion of Phosphogypsum through AMONI Route

In this valorization route, phosphogypsum (PG) is first homogenised, the homogenised PG is then reacted at ambient conditions with carbon dioxide (CO₂) and commercial aqueous ammonia in a pH-controlled, closed reactor system. To maximize the economic value and purity of the final products, the process includes an upscaled separation stage for phosphorus (P) and rare earth elements (REEs, recognized as critical raw materials) present in the PG matrix, this occurs before the filtration step. After filtration, two products are obtained: Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC), which is formed as a high-purity (>99%) filler material suited for applications in paper, plastics, rubbers, paints, etc. And ammonium sulphate ((NH₄)₂SO₄), is generated as a secondary product. The quality and yield of PCC depend on operational parameters such as solution temperature and chemical concentrations.

Included in the system boundaries (dashed line) both background and foreground inputs and outputs, aligned with ISO 14040/14044 standards for LCA:

- **Background System**
 - Extraction and processing of raw materials, aqueous ammonia, and any other chemicals used.
 - Energy Supply: The generation, transmission, and distribution of electricity and heat supplied to the reactor and auxiliary systems, accounting for the region's energy mix.
 - Emissions and resource use resulting from the transport of phosphogypsum, chemicals, and final products to and from the facility, including the types and amounts of fuels consumed.
- **Foreground System**
 - Mechanical or manual mixing to standardize the feed material.
 - The direct reaction of PG with CO₂ and commercial aqueous ammonia in a pH regulated.
 - Recovering, specific extraction of phosphorus and rare earth elements from the PG matrix before filtration.
 - Filtration stage yielding two primary products high-purity (>99%) precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) and ammonium sulfate ((NH₄)₂SO₄).

The following sources are excluded from both the system boundaries at this stage of the project:

- Use phase and application of products to manufacture new products in the industry.
- Distribution of valorized products beyond the laboratory gate.
- End-of-life treatment, or final disposal of products and by-products after they leave the industrial production facility.
- LCA environmental analyses exclude infrastructure (or capital goods) because the impacts from infrastructure are typically minimal per unit of output, especially for mass-produced products, and are challenging to quantify with high reliability. The economic analysis (LCC) will include all OPEX and CAPEX.

The use phase will be incorporated progressively as the project evolves, since the products generated are valuable inputs for a range of downstream industries (including cement, detergents, fertilizers, and paper, batteries, etc). As a result, the overall net environmental impact of the valorization routes will ultimately depend on adopting full cradle-to-grave system boundaries, accounting for potential benefits or substitution effects associated with displacing conventional materials.

2.2 Step 2 - Life cycle inventory (LCI) of each evaluated route

2.2.1 Procedure for Life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis

Life cycle inventory is the most resource-consuming step in LCA. The simplified procedure for inventory analysis typically begins with defining the system boundaries and flow models, followed by data collection, validation, allocation (if needed), and aggregation to relate data to the functional unit, as illustrated in the Figure 5 (based on UNEP LCA Training Kit, Module D). This structured approach ensures clarity, transparency, and reliability in the LCA results.

Mass and energy balances are fundamental components of Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). To complete the inventory data, ARDITEC has actively participated in the weekly regular meetings focused on developing the engineering plan. These meetings aim to deepen understanding of processes, scenarios, and operational conditions at both laboratory and pilot scales, ensuring accurate and comprehensive data collection for the Life Cycle Inventory. The following procedure was followed to collect and complete the life cycle inventory (LCI) data:

Figure 6 Simplified procedure for data inventory analysis

2.2.2 Life cycle inventory (LCI) sources

Even in a preliminary manner, primary data has been derived from the experimental work under FIC-Fighters project, LCI for NaOH route provided by USE (University of Sevilla) and for the LCI for AMONI route provided by ABO (Åbo Akademi University), project partners (see Table 4 and 5).

Figure 7 LCI data sources and flow to Impact Assessment

All modules were modelled using the European proxies from the Ecoinvent v3.11 database.

In the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), foreground data comprises specific processes and activities directly influenced within the FIC-Fighters project. At this stage, the data primarily reflects lab-scale system inputs, including reactant masses, energy use (estimated theoretically for stirring and filtration) and direct emissions such as CO₂ released during carbonation, collected data by USE. This lab-scale data forms the foundational input for the LCI and will, in the future, be complemented by pilot-scale data to better represent scaled-up processes.

Background data encompasses all processes beyond the project's direct control, such as electricity generation in Spain and precursor chemical synthesis (e.g., NaOH), sourced from the Ecoinvent v3.11 database. This background data supports sensitivity analyses in subsequent impact assessment phases, such as varying the energy mix, enabling a comprehensive and robust LCA framework for the project.

Therefore, while foreground data captures the FIC-Fighters project-specific advancements, background data supports scenario modelling and sensitivity checks that will enrich the interpretation of results and inform strategic decisions for enhancing sustainability beyond the immediate project boundaries. The integration of both data types ensures a comprehensive depiction of all environmental flows for the studied scenarios, enhancing the transparency and reproducibility of the assessment.

2.2.3 Life cycle inventory (LCI) Data Quality

The quality of data used in the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) is a critical determinant of the reliability and transparency of the assessment results. Data sources must be assessed for how current and regionally relevant they are, as well as their applicability to the specific technologies analysed. The matrix pedigree data quality is illustrated in Table 3. It shows that, at this stage of the project, data with good overall quality is being compiled.

Table 3 LCI data quality criteria

Criterion	Description
Temporal Representativeness	The data used in this inventory are based on experiments and lab-scale design specific to the year 2025
Geographical Representativeness	Region (European) Some examples tailored for LCI analysis involving at different regions (e.g., Spain, Finland, Portugal etc).
Technological Representativeness	Data suitability for the specific technology/process depending on the route.
Completeness	Relevant flows at this stage and processes are covered
Reliability	Source credibility, and data accuracy (not 100% at this stage)
Main assumptions/Proxies	Data is based on pilot/lab-scale setups, which may differ from full-scale industrial processes. Initial mass allocation method is selected. Some emission or waste data may be omitted as measurement is still not feasible at the laboratory stage. Proxies in the LCI data tables. NaOH and Ammonia are critical high impact in the evaluated routes, as those are proxies from ecoinvent v.11, more accurate to the specific precursor use in the process could assist to adjust reliability in further stages.

2.2.4 NaOH Route LCI: Inputs and Outputs

The LCA report in Deliverable 2.7 presents a preliminary life cycle assessment (LCA). At this stage, the life cycle inventory is based on primary data generated at laboratory scale from the experimental results currently available from the Universities: ABO (AMONI route) and USE (NaOH route). These data originate from laboratory-scale tests initially conducted using phosphogypsum from the Croatian case study. The selection of this phosphogypsum reflects the availability of consistent experimental data in this first iteration of the assessment and does not imply the exclusion of the other case studies. In the final version of this report (D2.8), the LCA will be extended to include scenarios that may cover the representative PG from case studies to evaluate the influence of residue-specific characteristics on the environmental results, thereby reflecting the iterative and progressive nature of the work.

Table 4 NaOH Route LCI - Inputs & Outputs

LCI	Raw materials	Function/process	Amount (g)
INPUTS	CaSO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	PG reaction (input burden zero)	1000
	Raw materials	Function/process	(tonne-km)
	Truck to port (Croatia)	PG transport, freight to the port	0,1
	Sea transport to Seville	PG transport, freight, CR - Spain	2,4
	Truck to Seville facility	PG transport, freight, lorry local	0,05
	Raw materials	Function/process	Amount (g)
	NaOH	PG reaction	417
	Water	PG reaction	4167
	Energy	Function/process	Amount (kWh)
	Manual	Pre-treatment unit (sieve)	0,0000
	Electricity	PG reactor unit (R1)	0,0025
	Electricity	Filtration (F1)	0,0017
	Natural /pools	Dryer	0,0000
	OUTPUTS	Emissions	Function/process
Water (vapour H ₂ O)		Emissions to air, evaporated after drying process but not impact	4264,31
Products		Function/process	Amount (g)
Na ₂ SO ₄		Product from R1	693,26
Ca(OH) ₂		Product from R1	429,17
Other products (dry base)		Product from R1	55,68
Total products	Total products from R1 without water	1178,10	
R2 – PG Carbonation reaction			
LCI	Raw materials	Function/process	Amount (g)
INPUTS	Ca(OH) ₂	Carbonation reactor (R2)	359,38
	Water Input	Carbonation reactor (R2)	4573
	CO ₂ input	Carbonation reactor (R2)	458
	CO ₂ captured	Calculated (not an input)	214
	Energy	Function/process	Amount (kWh)
	Energy	Electricity input stirring reaction R2	0,0069
	Energy	Filtration (F2)	0,0017

	Energy	Energy CO2 capture Direct Capture	0,4614
OUTPUTS	Emissions	Function/process	Amount (g)
	Water (vapour H2O)	Emissions to air, evaporated after drying process but not impact	3093,69
	CO ₂ release		244
	Products	Function/process	Amount (g)
	CaCO ₃	Product from R1	485,42
	Other products (dry base)	Product from R1	55,13
	Total products	Total products from R1 without water	540,54

2.2.5 AMONI Route LCI: Inputs and Outputs

Table 5 AMONI Route LCI - Inputs & Outputs

NH3 Route		FU= 1kg PG	
LCI	Raw materials	Function/process	Amount (g)
INPUTS	PG	PG	1000
	Raw materials	Function/process	(tonne-km)
	Truck to port (Croatia)	PG transport, freight to the port	0,1
	Sea transport to Turku	PG transport, freight, CR - Turku	1,0
	Truck to the facility	PG transport, freight, lorry local	0,05
	Raw materials	Function/process	Amount (g)
	NH ₃	Alkali for reaction with CO ₂	200
	CO ₂	Flue gas CO ₂ for carbonation	260
	Energy	Function/process	Amount (kWh)
	Manual	Pre-treatment, cleaning unit	0,000
	Electricity	Membrane separations	0,062
	Electricity	Other operations (Estimated value)	0,031
	Electricity	Energy to CO ₂ capture from Flue gas	0,03
	OUTPUTS	Emissions	Function/process
Air		Emissions to air, CO ₂ released	NA
Water		Wastewater	26,00
Products		Function/process	Amount (g)
PCC		Filtration unit - output	569,70
Ammonium sulfate		Ion selective membrane - output	751,20
Valuable metals		Ion exchange membrane - output	20,00
NH ₄ Cl		Membrane electrolizer – output, recover for cleaning	12,40
Water	PG crystal water, Ion selective membrane - output	104,53	

2.3 Step 3 – LCA Impact assessment across evaluated routes

Each valorization route is modelled separately, using the same functional unit for consistency. Key impact metrics, such as climate change and water use, among others are evaluated, with results expressed as environmental impact values based on normalization and weighting. These values are calculated through characterization and combined into a Single Score, measured in Eco-Points (Pts). The step 3 represents the core of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). The Figure below highlights the selected elements considered in the system modelling, with detailed results to be provided in the **Chapter 3** of this report.

Functional unit	1 kg of PG
Method	EF3.1 (adapted)
Geographical representativeness	Europe
Data set	Ecoinvent v3.11
Allocation	Outputs mass allocation
Data type	Primary data (FIC-FIGHTERS experimental cases at laboratory scale)
Software	Simapro v10.02

Figure 8 Settings to modelling environmental impact

As shown in the previous illustration, at the outset of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) project, the certainty and accuracy of impact assessment results are limited by preliminary data, assumptions, and model simplifications. However, as the project advances, data quality will improve through the collection of primary data, refinement of model parameters, and validation. This progressive improvement will result in more reliable and robust outcomes.

2.4 Step 4 - Interpretation

In this step the Life Cycle Impact Assessment, results from Step 3 are critically analyzed to identify environmental trade-offs, and the net benefit impacts. Comparing the environmental impacts of the two phosphogypsum valorization routes focusing on climate change and water use, among others, guiding future improvements or scenarios to explore in the upcoming months of the project.

It needs to be emphasized that this is a preliminary assessment with limited impact categories analysed. The comparisons and discussion will be outlined in the **chapter 4** of this report.

3 Life Cycle Assessment across the evaluated routes

3.1 Hotspots identification

This section presents an analysis of environmental hotspots. The analysis focuses on identifying key contributors to environmental impacts at different levels of the process for each route.

3.1.1 NaOH Route

For the NaOH route two complementary perspectives are evaluated:

LCA Perspective	Description
Overall, NAOH route hotspots (Figure 9)	Environmental contributions aggregated for the full NaOH route process.
Reaction 1 hotspots (Figure 10)	Breakdown of impacts within the first reaction stage. To better understand specific environmental relative contributions within Reaction 1. Pinpoint specific hotspots for action.

Figure 8 shows the relative contributions of major process steps and key inputs to a wide range of environmental impact categories, as determined by SimaPro LCA modelling for **1 kg phosphogypsum** input and intermediate portlandite conversion to CaCO₃ (Reaction 2), including by-products. The assessment uses the EF 3.1 method (adapted), with results normalized and weighted.

Out of the 16 impact categories evaluated, “Portlandite” is the dominant positive contributor to climate impacts (i.e., emissions), primarily due to upstream impacts from reagent production in Reaction 1 (PG reaction with NaOH) and its associated supply chain. The process also features a significant negative climate contribution, reflecting the CO₂ permanently stored in the mineral (CaCO₃ main product).

Figure 9 Overall NAOH route hotspots environmental relative contribution

Electricity demand for CO₂ capture constitutes a major environmental burden across most categories. Additionally, energy use for Reaction 2 (Portlandite Carbonation) and Filtration 2 has a lesser, but notable, impact, highlighting the ongoing need for improving process efficiency and optimizing energy sourcing at the pilot scale.

Portlandite is the primary driver for toxicity impact, as well as freshwater ecotoxicity, this is stem from upstream emissions of intermediates in reagent synthesis of Reaction 1. For the resource use category fossil resources: “Energy for CO₂ capture” stands out as a main hotspot, underlining fossil-fuel-derived electricity is a critical impact lever.

As illustrated in Figure 9, the influence on environmental impact categories varies considerably, meaning that effective improvements must be tailored to the largest contributors in each category.

At this stage, given the focus and maturity of the process, analysis will prioritize the categories of climate change and water use. As the project progresses, a comprehensive evaluation of resource use, human toxicity, and across all impact categories will be carried out. The following figure 9 illustrates the main environmental impacts originate primarily from upstream processes to produce portlandite in Reaction 1 and its associated supply chain.

Figure 10 Reaction 1 environmental relative contribution

Dominant hotspots in Reaction 1 come from the use of NaOH, which accounts for over 75% of the relative contribution in most impact categories. This is primarily due to the high upstream environmental burden associated with sodium hydroxide production from Ecoinvent database (its substantial energy requirements, resource use, and associated emissions throughout the supply chain). Notably, the water use category diverges, with the utilization of tap water exceeding 50% contribution; this reflects the direct intake of freshwater in the process rather than upstream chemical impacts. Such results anticipate that effective impact mitigation strategies should focus on sourcing “greener” NaOH, optimizing reagent efficiency, and improving water management practices to address the primary environmental drivers identified.

3.1.2 AMONI Route

For the AMONI route, the evaluation was done at this stage of the project only for overall system. Figure 11 provides a clear breakdown of the environmental hotspots across multiple impact categories, as determined by SimaPro LCA modelling for 1 kg phosphogypsum input through AMONI route.

It is evident that ammonia is the principal environmental hotspot, representing the highest impact across most categories, including water and resource use, fossil depletion, toxicity, and ecotoxicity. Electricity demand (especially for membrane systems and CO₂ capture from flue gas), emerges as a key secondary contributor, particularly influencing land use and ionising radiation categories. Notably, the negative bar in the climate change category demonstrates that CO₂ mineralization within the process offsets a significant portion of the total greenhouse gas emissions, underscoring the climate mitigation potential of the technology.

Environmental Impacts from transport (blue bars) is relevant in the categories accounting particulate matter, eutrophication and acidification due to the use of conventional fuels. Minor but relevant impacts also arise from wastewater and other equipment use, particularly in categories related to eutrophication and toxicity. Overall, the figure highlights the need to prioritize reductions in ammonia use and to optimize the energy sources and efficiency of critical process stages to improve the environmental sustainability of the AMONI route as an overall system.

Figure 11 AMONI route environmental relative contributions overall process

Regarding impact derived from transport, it is true that these impacts could be reduced if a mobile plant is deployed, as the distance transport of PG from Croatia to Finland can be avoided. All these parameters will be further evaluated throughout the project and incorporated into sensitivity analyses.

3.2 Climate change impact

Europe’s climate objectives and regulatory framework focus on significantly cutting greenhouse gas emissions, aiming for at least a 55% reduction by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050. Moreover, CO₂ evaluation is prioritized at this stage because it is the main driver of climate change, and the carbonation processes in PG valorization act as CO₂ sinks, making this impact category essential to evaluate in depth along the project. Other indicators like acidification, resource depletion, land use, human toxicity among others will also be included in the final report analysis for a comprehensive environmental assessment.

3.2.1 NaOH route

Overall, NAOH route and the related CO₂ emissions attributed to each input is depicted in Figure 12. Net emissions remain positive due to the significant contribution of NaOH in the proposed route, even though the mineral outputs provide substantial CO₂ sequestration benefits, this is not sufficient to offset the upstream impacts. Specifically, processing 1 kg of PG requires 430 g of NaOH, which contributes 0.332 kg CO₂ to the total net value per kg PG, in addition to other inputs such as energy use and PG transport. Therefore, to reduce emissions or achieve net-negative results per kg PG treated, it is necessary to both optimize yield of valuable products and minimize NaOH input.

Energy use for the CO₂ capture process remains low but in cases where the energy requirement for direct capture increases, the net CO₂ emissions may be even higher. Sensitivity analysis on the influence of required energy for CO₂ capture is included in section 4.3. Regarding inputs from transport, it is true that these impacts could be reduced if a mobile plant is deployed, as long-distance transport of PG from Croatia to Spain can be avoided. All these parameters will be further evaluated throughout the project and incorporated into sensitivity analyses.

Figure 12 Climate change impact associated with processing 1 kg of PG

In summary, when the functional unit is defined as 1 kg of phosphogypsum (see Figure 10), total system emissions are calculated by adding emissions from producing portlandite, sodium sulphate, and other by-products. From this sum, the CO₂ captured during carbonation was subtracted. The net result is a positive emission of approximately 0.152 kg CO₂-equivalent per kg of phosphogypsum treated. This means, upstream production processes still contribute enough emissions to result in a net positive value. It is important to note that these data are preliminary and may vary with more refined experimental design.

3.2.2 AMONI route

Overall, the AMONI route and the CO₂ emissions attributed to each input are shown in Figure 13. The positive net CO₂ emissions (green bar) mainly come from ammonia use, which has a high carbon footprint according to Ecoinvent data for this chemical.

Specifically, the production of anhydrous ammonia (NH₃) is highly energy-intensive, with a typical carbon footprint ranging between 1.6 and 2.8 kg CO₂-e per kg NH₃, depending on the energy source and production technology. According to the Ecoinvent database V.11 (European NH₃, anhydrous, liquid), the emission factor adopted in this study is 2.73 kg CO₂-e per kg NH₃.

It is important to highlight the production of 1 kg of PCC is likely to sequester a substantial amount of CO₂, suggesting that a full offset, or even a net negative CO₂ impact could be achieved when evaluated at the product level.

Figure 13 Climate change impact associated with processing 1 kg of PG

4 Interpretation

Before presenting the scenario analysis, it is important to define how environmental burdens are handled in processes that generate multiple outputs. In multi-product systems, some outputs may provide environmental benefits (such as CO₂ capture during carbonation), while others, like ammonium sulphate or other marketable by-products, may carry a positive carbon footprint. To fairly account for these contrasting effects, allocation is applied to divide the environmental burdens among co-products according to a chosen criterion. The selected allocation method directly influences the results of the LCA, and thorough justification is required to ensure consistency, transparency, and alignment with circular economy principles. Common allocation approaches include mass-based (used method in this preliminary assessment), energy-based, economic, and system expansion methods.

The allocation approach is constantly being revised to reflect updated data along the project, product uses, and process insights, ensuring that the LCA results remain accurate and representative of the multi-product system.

4.1 Comparative scenarios

4.1.1 NaOH route: Climate change impact

The carbonation of portlandite is governed by both reaction kinetics and mass transfer phenomena, which together influence the total CO₂ uptake achievable in the system. Chemically, the carbonation proceeds via a dissolution-precipitation mechanism: portlandite (Ca(OH)₂) dissolves into calcium and hydroxide ions, while dissolved CO₂ forms carbonic acid in water, subsequently reacting with calcium ions to precipitate calcium carbonate (CaCO₃).

Figure 14 Climate change impact associated with production of 1 kg of CaCO₃

When taken as the functional unit 1 kg of calcium carbonate (Figure 14), only the proportionally allocated impacts (34%) of the environmental burden from the portlandite (from the upstream R1) utilized for its production are considered. By applying this mass allocation and factoring in the credit for the CO₂ sequestered, the net emissions in this assessment may reach negative values. True net benefit depends on upstream impacts: if portlandite formation is energy-intensive, high fossil electricity may diminish the carbon sink effect. Decentralized, renewable-powered processing has the greatest climate advantage. For every 1 mole of CaCO₃ produced, exactly 1 mole (44.0 g) of CO₂ is fixed (orange bar). Four scenarios were conducted at laboratory scale by USE, each designed to examine the influence of varying process parameters outlined in the table below.

Table 6 LCA scenarios for the NaOH route: evaluating the carbonation (Reaction 2)

Scenario	Device configuration	d _i /D	rpm	(g/L)	CO ₂ (L/min)	Reaction time (min)	CO ₂ uptake (%)	Increase in temperature (°C)	COMPARATIVE
S1	4	0.61	450	50	2	14.2	91.8	11.8	Lower stirring speed required, very low CO ₂ loss but low processed concentration
S2	4a	0,43	700	50	2	13.8	94.5	11.9	
S3	8	0.61	550	70	4	14.6	62.5	16.0	Higher agitation speed required, greater CO ₂ loss but higher processed concentration
S4	10	0.61	600	100	6.5	17.2	46.7	23.0	Much higher agitation speed required, much greater CO ₂ loss but much higher processed concentration

For each scenario, a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was modelled to evaluate how these changes affect the overall environmental performance and CO₂ sequestration efficiency. This approach enables a systematic comparison of the impacts associated with each operational configuration, providing insights that guide process optimization and sustainable scale-up.

Figure 15 Four evaluated scenarios - Climate change impact

Scenario 2 achieved the highest percentage of CO₂ captured, resulting in a greater amount of CO₂ chemically stored as CaCO₃ compared to the other scenarios. Although this scenario showed minor increases in energy consumption due to changes in impeller design and stirring speed (rpm), the slightly higher water input required did not offset the net carbon capture benefits.

From an LCA perspective, incomplete carbonation resulting from kinetic limitations and mass transfer resistances reduces the real CO₂ sequestration relative to theoretical stoichiometric limits. Therefore, process and reactor designs must optimize these factors to maximize total CO₂ uptake, ensuring the environmental benefits of mineral carbonation are fully realized. Overall, Scenario 2 demonstrated the most negative net CO₂ emissions, reflecting superior carbon sequestration performance despite the marginally increased energy and water inputs.

4.1.2 NaOH route: Water use impact

In the first reaction step, approximately 4 L of water are required per kilogram of phosphogypsum to dissolve sodium hydroxide and enable the conversion of CaSO₄·2H₂O into soluble sodium sulfate. From a life-cycle assessment perspective, this water represents a freshwater input ($\approx 0.0043 \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ PG}$) in Figure 16, which is the proportional charge to the required portlandite for producing 1kgCaCO₃. Most of it subsequently leaves the system as water vapor when the Na₂SO₄ solution is dried or naturally evaporated in open ponds. Although this vapor release does not generate greenhouse gases or persistent emissions, it is still treated as consumed water because evaporation removes it from the local freshwater resource base.

From an LCA perspective, the results in Figure 16 indicate that when water re-use in reactor R2 (carbonation process) the system performs significantly better than the conventional system in terms of water scarcity-related impacts. The total water deprivation is reduced from approximately 0.65 m³ in the

conventional case to around 0.44 m³ with water re-use, corresponding to an overall reduction of about 30–35%.

The dominant contributor to water deprivation in both scenarios is tap water consumption (in reactor R2). In the conventional system, this stage accounts for a substantial share of the total impact, whereas under water re-use scenario its contribution is reduced by nearly half. This confirms that freshwater abstraction is the main hotspot for water deprivation in the system. Water deprivation associated with electricity consumption (R2 and F2) is negligible across both scenarios, and electricity used for CO₂ capture contributes only marginally to the overall water footprint.

Figure 16 Water use impact associated with production of 1 kg of CaCO₃

For the second reaction, aqueous carbonation proceeds by dissolution of Ca(OH)₂, CO₂ hydration, Ca²⁺–CO₃²⁻ nucleation and CaCO₃ precipitation. The overall environmental relevance of this category (water use) will depend on the analysed region, in reference mainly to local water scarcity.

4.1.3 AMONI route: Climate change impact

Mass allocation among the co-products will be applied to distribute the environmental impacts proportionally. Figures 17-19 show the CO₂ emissions per 1 kg of each corresponding product.

In the cradle to gate system studied, three main co-products are produced from phosphogypsum processing: ammonium sulphate (a fertilizer), recovered metals (valuable secondary raw materials), and precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC). The PCC (Figure 17) plays a key role by providing permanent carbon dioxide storage within the cradle to gate boundary, sequestering approximately 0.44 kilograms of CO₂ per kilogram of PCC produced. This carbon dioxide sequestration significantly reduces the carbon footprint of the PCC product, which explains why it exhibits a notably lower and, in some cases, net negative global warming potential when impacts are calculated per kilogram of product.

By contrast, ammonium sulphate (Figure 18) and the recovered metals (Figure 19) do not sequester CO₂ within the cradle-to-gate boundary and therefore carry the upstream burdens associated with precursors and reagents, most notably the carbon-intensive production of anhydrous ammonia. Using the Ecoinvent/market factor for European anhydrous ammonia (used in this study) of ≈2.73 kg CO₂-e per kg NH₃ materially increases the process GWP; these emissions are not offset by direct CO₂ storage in those co-products.

Figure 17 Climate change impact associated with production of 1 kg of PCC

Further analysis will be conducted across the project duration, and re-definition of the system boundaries will address final conclusions. For instance, if the recovered metals substitute primary metal production or if ammonium sulphate replaces conventionally produced fertilizer, these avoided burdens would only be reflected under system expansion or substitution. Including these effects in subsequent stages of the assessment, would further enhance the overall climate and other environmental indicators performance of each route.

Figure 18 Climate change impact associated with production of 1 kg of Ammonia sulfate

Figure 19 Climate change impact associated with production of 1kg of Valuable metals

The allocation is a critical methodological choice in the FIC-Fighters' LCA evaluation and will therefore be examined in detail for both the NaOH and AMONI routes. LCA allocation is the method used to divide environmental impacts among multiple co-products of a system. It is typically based on physical relationships (e.g., mass or economic value), depending on the goal and scope of the study.

The current preliminary analysis includes only the mass flows and in the upcoming analysis, LCA allocation may be performed in an economic perspective, using the revenue potential of each co-product.

4.2 Comparative LCA to the baseline (business-as-usual stockpiles)

The baseline scenario represents inaction, the current state where phosphogypsum is simply stockpiled as waste without valorization efforts. This long-term stockpiling leads to increased environmental burdens, most notably a higher acidification potential compared to valorization routes. Due to limited specific data on phosphogypsum stockpiling, the Ecoinvent v3.11 dataset for “treatment of waste gypsum, sanitary landfill, Europe without Switzerland” was used as the best available proxy, enabling a preliminary environmental performance comparison across multiple impact categories.

Figure 20 Comparative environmental impact categories vs the PG stockpiles under the same FU

Although this dataset does not capture all site-specific impacts such as radionuclide emissions or leachate impacts among others, it provides a baseline for comparison. The SP scenario involves prolonged land occupation, permanent land transformation, and risks of contamination to adjacent soils and waterways. In contrast, valorization routes reduce land-use impacts by converting PG into useful products and avoiding virgin material extraction.

In line with Chen et al. (2025) [11], the baseline Stockpile of Phosphogypsum (SP) scenario exhibits a higher acidification potential (AP) compared to PG valorization routes, reflecting the environmental burdens of long-term disposal. Other impact categories remain difficult to quantify through LCA due to data limitations and site-specific uncertainties.

4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis in the context of LCA focuses on how variations in input data or assumptions affect the outcomes of a model or study. It helps to understand the reliability, robustness, and critical factors influencing results. In this section we will vary key parameters and evaluate the impact in two key environmental categories: water use and climate change.

4.3.1 NaOH route: Water use impact

Re-use process water for two cycles carbonation batches (reaction 2) is usually feasible with modest treatment (settling + filtration + pH/alkalinity management). It can cut total freshwater demand (m³ depriv.) roughly in half as presented in light blue bar in Figure 16, for that part of the process, but performance, product morphology, and downstream treatment needs may change as dissolved ions and colloids accumulate [9]. From an LCA perspective, further pilot-scale analysis is needed to evaluate the trade-offs between freshwater savings and the additional energy, chemicals, and maintenance required to treat recirculated water. It is expected that for a single reuse cycle, minimal treatment steps such as settling, decantation, and filtration can keep energy inputs low. The preliminary results in water reuse benefits may reach 39%, as illustrated in the figure 16.

Figure 21 Water use impact in four evaluated scenarios

The unit “m³ water deprived” refers to the potential amount of water that becomes unavailable for other users or ecosystems because of the implementation of this route. The red area means the 39% of potential reduction reached for Scenarios 1 and 2 when implementing one cycle of reuse, as outlined in the experimental design by USE. Since Scenario 2 showed a greater potential for net CO₂ reduction, but involves higher water use under conventional conditions (blue area), reusing water for one additional cycle would lower the overall impact to levels comparable to or even lower than those observed in Scenario 4.

Some other recommendations from environmental point of view that can be evaluated in further experimental design, the use of reclaimed or brackish water to input in the first reaction. Since the reaction chemistry tolerates moderate salinity, high-quality freshwater is not strictly necessary. Replacing it with treated wastewater, cooling-tower blowdown, or brackish groundwater can markedly reduce the process’s blue-water footprint. This substitution shifts the inventory from freshwater withdrawal to non-competitive sources, improving the LCA water-scarcity indicator without major equipment modifications.

4.3.2 NaOH route: Carbon Removal Efficiency (CRE)

Carbon removal efficiency (CRE) is defined as the proportion of net atmospheric CO₂ removed in relation to the total amount of CO₂ that could be theoretically stored in the product (CaCO₃). The formula ensures that the real climate benefit of the process is measured, not just theoretical CO₂ fixed [10], but what is actually removed from the atmosphere when all life cycle emissions of the proposed route are subtracted. CRE is expressed as a percentage:

$$CRE = \frac{\text{Net CO}_2 \text{ Removed}}{\text{Total CO}_2 \text{ stoichiometrically stored}} \times 100$$

- Net CO₂ Removed: CO₂ permanently sequestered, minus all direct and indirect life cycle emissions attributable to energy, feedstock, and processing steps.
- Total CO₂ Stoichiometrically Stored: Theoretical maximum CO₂ that can be incorporated into CaCO₃ by the mineral carbonation process.

The blue trendline in the Figure 22 below, directly visualizes this efficiency across Spain, Portugal, and Croatia, revealing country-level differences. High carbon removal efficiency ensures that most of the process’s theoretical sequestration capacity is translated into real climate-positive results. Low efficiency signals engineering bottlenecks, such as poor reaction yield, excessive energy use, or carbon-intensive input chains.

CRE depends not only on how much CO₂ is stored in CaCO₃, but also on the emissions generated during its production, with electricity being a major source of these emissions. The Figure 22 depicts the comparison highlights how sensitive CRE is to the electricity mix. Because electricity carbon intensity varies widely by country, the same process leads to very different net CO₂ removal outcomes.

Figure 22 Carbon removal efficiency vs the electricity carbon intensity

For FIC-Fighters project, three countries with foreseen potential for future application were selected in this sensitivity analysis at this stage. Under the evaluated conditions, Spain shows the highest CRE (30.5%), meaning that nearly one-third of the theoretical carbon storage results in real atmospheric CO₂ removal. Portugal follows closely with 27.3%, still indicating a system capable of credible negative emissions. In contrast, Croatia reaches only 18.2%, showing how a more carbon-intensive electricity grid can significantly reduce the climate benefit of the process.

However, achievable removal efficiencies do not depend on electricity alone. They are also limited by internal process factors such as conversion yields, reactor design, and control of side reactions. In particular, the efficiency of portlandite synthesis from phosphogypsum and the effectiveness of CO₂ absorption determine the maximum amount of CO₂ that can be removed per ton of waste treated.

5 Circularity performance assessment

The circular economy is central to the FIC-Fighters project, because it transforms phosphogypsum, a hazardous industrial waste into valuable resources. By closing material loops and reintegrating waste into production cycles across multiple industries, the project aims at reducing waste disposal, mitigates environmental impact, and avoid use of virgin raw materials in the downstream.

WP2 aims to optimise the two routes and implementing circularity of proposed technologies and identify opportunities to integrate circular economy strategies. Task 2.5 focuses on developing comprehensive guidelines for implementing circular systemic solutions. This task will integrate the results from both the environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the economic Life Cycle Costing (LCC) studies to assess how the system contributes to a circular economy. By doing so, it ensures that the FIC-Fighters approach supports comprehensive sustainability. The current deliverable, D2.7, provides a preliminary report on the methodology for Task 2.5. The complete guidelines will be presented in the final report, D2.12, "Guidelines for Circular Systemic Solutions", which is scheduled for month 48 of the project.

5.1 Theoretical foundation

The Circular Economy (CE) emphasizes transitioning from linear production and economies, characterized by resource depletion and environmental degradation from the processing consumption-disposal model, towards promoting closed-loop systems. While environmental and economic assessments typically follow standardized methodologies, circularity has only recently begun to acquire formalized measurement and assessment frameworks. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation (EMF) provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating circularity, with indicators addressing material flows, product design, business models, and system-level impacts [12,13], EMF's toolkits, including the Circular Economy in Cities Project Guide and the Measurement and Reporting Overview, support practitioners in implementing consistent and meaningful assessments across diverse contexts.

Complementing these practical guidelines, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has introduced the ISO 59000 series (ISO 59004, ISO 59020) [14,15], to provide internationally recognized standards for circular-economy terminology, business-model transition, and circularity performance measurement. By combining practitioner-selected indicators, guideline frameworks from EMF and European projects, and emerging ISO standards, circularity assessment is becoming more structured, though widespread harmonization across sectors is still in progress.

5.2 Circularity assessment indicators

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) serves as a foundational basis for circular economy analysis, as depicted in Figure 1, based on the new ISO 59020 standard for circularity). By quantifying environmental impacts across the FIC-FIGHTERS products lifecycle, LCA will provide essential data that informs circularity strategies and guides effective decision making within the broader circular economy framework.

According to ISO 59020, use material flow analysis and circularity performance scores to benchmark the baseline against the innovative scenario, highlighting reductions and improvements (e.g., percentage

increase in recycled material, decrease in virgin resource use, lowered waste/emissions). The key circularity indicators are structured into mandatory and optional categories and span the following areas:

- **Mandatory Core Circularity Indicators:**
 - Resource Inflows: Measures the amount and type of resources (especially non-renewable and renewable) entering the system.
 - Resource Outflows: Assesses output streams, focusing on waste, emissions, and materials leaving the system, including recovery, reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling rates.

- **Optional Indicators:**
 - Energy: Evaluates energy use and the share of renewable energy in processes.
 - Water: Monitors water use and circularity in water management.
 - Economic: Includes factors like costs, revenues, and value preservation through circular actions.

Figure 23 Circularity performance indicators

FIC-Fighters valorizes waste into products and by-products for use in cement, fertilizers, detergents, and batteries, helping to close material loops and support a circular economy. A set of key performance indicators (KPIs) is recommended. These preliminary KPIs are defined to provide measurable criteria to assess the efficiency, circularity, and sustainability of converting PG into valuable products such as CaCO₃, precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC), fertilizers, detergents, and cement additives.

Table 7 Indicators to track circularity and sustainability design

KPI	Definition	Why it is advisable for PG valorization
Carbon Efficiency Removal (CER)	Total GHG emissions of the process / stoichiometric CO ₂ potential of the product × 100.	Quantifies how efficiently the PG valorization process turns waste into a carbon sink, considering both sequestration and emissions. Helps optimise routes for maximum net carbon benefit.
Circularity: Material Reuse Ratio (MRR)	Fraction of PG mass converted into valuable products/ total PG input.	Measures efficiency in diverting PG from stockpiles into new raw materials for cement additives, fertilizers etc.

Energy use Efficiency	Total energy use/total valuable product	Tracks energy consumption of PG routes to maximize Net CO ₂ , reduce other environmental impacts and operational costs.
Water use Efficiency	m ³ of water deprived per kg of product	Ensures efficient water use in the processing routes, reducing effluent and freshwater consumption.

5.2.1 Key circular actions

ISO 59020 lists key circular actions (design, reduce, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, recycle, regenerate, etc.) as relevant strategies to measure in the circular economy framework. It aligns with the approach, starting with high value “inner” loops (reuse, repair) and going outwards to recycling. In the context of phosphogypsum valorisation, one or more of the following strategies will be implemented: Reuse, Repair, Remanufacture, and Recycling. Table 7 visually prioritizes the inner technical loops using the Butterfly Diagram.

Table 8 Circular Economy Butterfly Diagram - key actions

Circular Economy Butterfly Diagram

Preliminary evaluating the phosphogypsum valorisation

Reuse: Using cleaned phosphogypsum directly in construction applications constitutes reuse, as the material is not fundamentally altered but used again. It may be aligned when reusing the unreacted and cleaned PG waste.

Repair: Process controls maintaining material quality. Repair is not directly analogous to the process proposed in FIC-FIGHTERS.

Remanufacture: Treating and carbonating phosphogypsum to new products. The chemical treatment of phosphogypsum to portlandite and carbonation to CaCO₃ exemplifies remanufacturing by creating new value-added products from waste. *(Aligned to FIC-Fighters process)*

Recycle: Turn PG waste into raw materials. Chemical recycling of phosphogypsum via mineral recovery and reintegration into production cycles would close material loops, minimizing virgin resource extraction.

6 LCA preliminary conclusions

- The preliminary results suggest that producing 1 kg of CaCO_3 from phosphogypsum waste via the NaOH route offers significant climate benefits, with net CO_2 savings of -0.152 kg under scenarios 1 and 2, as highlighted in Section 4.1.1 and Figure 14. Achieving consistently zero or negative emissions, however, will require more precise data on the energy needed for CO_2 capture from the atmosphere or flue gas, as well as the energy demands of the chemical reactions and auxiliary processes. In contrast, the AMONI route for producing 1 kg of PCC shows a lower climate benefit of -0.04 kg CO_2 (Section 4.2.1, Figure 18). It is also evident that co-products such as valuable metals and ammonium sulfate, or sodium nitrate should be evaluated against appropriate baselines, as they are not carbon sink products and may influence the overall environmental assessment.
- This preliminary assessment highlights that the definition of the functional unit and the approach to co-product allocation critically shape environmental impact results. In this preliminary LCA, mass allocation was used to distribute cradle-to-gate impacts across co-products for both routes, providing transparency but potentially underestimating benefits from co-product substitution. Consistent and transparent reporting of these methodological choices is essential for producing robust, interpretable, and reproducible results. Further analysis will refine these assessments as the FIC-Fighters project progresses.
- At later development phases, the functional unit will be refined to reflect the actual performance or function of the final commercial product (for example, accounting for required product characteristics, purity, or technical application) thus supporting market-relevant comparisons and aligning the assessment with the product's end use and quality.
- In the early stages of NaOH plant engineering design, the potential for CO_2 removal in phosphogypsum (PG) valorization is strongly influenced by technical and operational factors, including external energy input, conversion efficiency, reactor configuration, and control of side reactions. High-yield portlandite production, combined with optimized CO_2 absorption kinetics, defines the theoretical maximum CO_2 capture per kilogram of PG processed. To support the design, a set of preliminary key performance indicators (KPIs) has been proposed, providing measurable criteria to assess efficiency, circularity, and sustainability in converting PG into valuable products (see Table 6). These KPIs may guide informed decision-making, helping align engineering strategies with environmental and process performance objectives.
- Compared to conventional phosphogypsum stockpiles, the evaluated scenarios demonstrate significant environmental benefits, especially regarding acidification and land use impacts linked to long-term disposal. However, quantifying other impact categories remains challenging due to data limitations and site-specific variability. Future analyses will focus on a more comprehensive comparison of these benefits, including land use reduction and environmental improvements relative to current stockpiling practices.
- The Al-waste NaOH treatment route for phosphogypsum valorization will be further evaluated in future studies. This approach holds significant promise due to the positive environmental impact of utilizing industrial residues instead of pure raw materials. By converting waste streams into valuable inputs, this route can reduce resource consumption and associated emissions, advancing circular economy goals while enhancing process sustainability.

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